

Chromosome Analysis of Four Species of Histeridae Beetles (Coleoptera : Histeridae)

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Abstract

Karyological investigations were carried out on adult male individuals of four species of Histeridae beetles viz. *Hister quadrimaculatus* L., *Platysoma cambojensis* Mars., *Platysoma atratum* Er. and *Platylister strialis* Mars. *H. quadrimaculatus* L. possesses $2n = 26 : 12+Xy_p$, and *P. cambojensis* Mars. and *P. atratum* Er. possesses $2n = 28 : 13+Xy_p$ and *P. strialis* Mars. exhibited $2n = 20 : 9+Xy_p$ sex mechanism. Mitosis and meiosis has been described and discussed.

Keywords

Coleoptera, Histeridae, Sex chromosome mechanism, Autosome, Karyotype.

Introduction

The Coleopterans are generally known as beetles. It is the largest order not only of Insecta but also of the whole animal kingdom. It is divided in to four suborders viz. Adepaga, Archostemata, Myxophaga and Polyphaga. The suborder Polyphaga is sub divided in to Haplogastra and Symphiogastra (Richard and Davis, 1979). The Haplogastra comprises four super families: Scarabaeoidea, Hydrophiloidea, Staphylinioidea and Histeroidea. Histeroidea consist of three families, Sphaeritidae, Histeridae and Synteliidae (Kryzhanovsky and Reykhardt, 1976). Histeridae family contains 3,900 species found worldwide (Mazur, 1997). It is a large and diverse family. The beetles range in size, shape and colour. These predatory feeders are most active at night and will fake death if they feel threatened. The body forms of these beetles are typically rounded and ovoid but some are flat and rectangular. Hister beetles are found in various habitats, but each Hister species occupies certain specific ecological niches. Hister beetles or clown beetles live in dung, carrion, sand area, under tree bark, dead vegetation, ant/termite colonies and mammal burrows. Certain species are used in the control of livestock pests that infest dung and to control houseflies. They are predacious and will even eat other Hister beetles. As far as its cytology is concerned Histeridae is a neglected family. Keeping in view the economic importance and paucity of literature on the chromosomes of this group the present investigations were under taken. All species are new addition to the cytology of this group.

Objective of study

To investigate and document the chromosomal number, karyotype structure, and sex chromosome mechanism (Xy_p type) in four Histeridae beetle species, adding new cytological data to a poorly studied but economically important insect family.

Review of Literature

The Coleoptera is the largest insect order, with Histeridae being a diverse family of over 3,900 species worldwide. These beetles play important ecological and pest-control roles. However, cytogenetic studies on Histeridae are scarce. Prior work (Yadav & Dange, 1988-1990; Dange, 1991) has reported chromosome counts for only 26 species. Most exhibit the Xy_p sex chromosome system and a modal diploid number of $2n = 20$. This study expands that limited cytological database. Dange et al. (2013) investigated the karyotypes of two Histeridae beetle species, *Pachylister ceylenus* and *Platylister procerus*, reporting diploid numbers of 22 and 26 with an Xy_p sex chromosome system. Their findings offer valuable cytogenetic data, but chromosomal studies on Histeridae remain limited, indicating a need for further research in this group.

Methodology

Adult male individuals of *Hister quadrimaculatus* L., *Platysoma cambojensis* Mars., *P. atratum* Er. and *Platylister strialis* Mars. constituted the materials for the present investigations. All the beetles were collected under the mercury vapour lamps during June to August 2025 from Ratlam (Madhya Pradesh). Chromosome preparations were made following Yadav and Lyapunova (1983).

Result and Discussion

***Hister quadrimaculatus* L.**

The diploid number of 26 chromosomes was observed at the spermatogonial metaphase (fig.01). The karyotype comprises seven metacentric pairs (pairs 1-4, 7, 8, and 10), five sub metacentric (pairs 5, 6, 9, 11 and 12) of chromosomes, the X chromosome was metacentric and y is minute and acrocentric (fig.02).

12 dumb-bell shaped autosomal bivalents and the sex bivalent Xy_p constitute the metaphase I plate (Fig.09). The first meiotic reductional division result in the formation of two types of metaphase II plates one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig.10).

The male chromosome formula is $12AA+Xy_p$.

***Platysoma cambojensis* Mars.**

Spermatogonial metaphase (fig.03) revealed the diploid number of 28 chromosomes. The karyotype comprises 13 pairs of autosomes and the sex chromosomes X and y, autosome pairs 1-5 are metacentric while pairs 6-13 and X chromosome are sub metacentric, y is dot-shaped and is the smallest element of the karyotype (fig.04). Appreciable size difference exists between the autosomes constituting pairs 1 and 2 while the remaining autosomes showed a gradation in size. As such, autosomes of pair 1 are the 'marker chromosomes'.

Metaphase I constituted 13 autosomal bivalents, mostly ring-shaped and the sex pseudo bivalent forming a parachute (fig.11). The first reductional division result in the formation of two types of metaphase II plates one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig.12).

The male chromosome formula is $13AA+Xy_p$.

***P. atratum* Er.**

Spermatogonial metaphase exhibited a diploid set of 28 chromosomes (fig.05). Autosome pairs 1-4 are metacentric, pairs 5-9, 11 and 12 are sub metacentric, whereas pairs 10 and 13 and the sex chromosomes X and y are acrocentric (fig.06).

13 dumbbell shaped autosomal bivalents and the sex bivalent Xy_p constituted the metaphase I plate (fig.13). The first meiotic division being reductional it results in the formation of two types of metaphase II plates one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig.14).

The male chromosome formula is $13AA+Xy_p$.

***Platylister strialis* Mars.**

Spermatogonial metaphase (fig.07) revealed a diploid set of 20 chromosomes. The karyotype is composed of nine pairs of autosomes and the sex chromosomes X and y (fig.08). Two pairs of autosomes (pairs 1 and 5) and the X chromosome are metacentric, six pairs of autosomes (pair 2-4, 6-8) are sub metacentric, autosome pair nine is acrocentric whereas y is a minute spherical chromosome.

Metaphase I possesses nine autosomal bivalents, mostly dumb-bell shaped (Fig.15). The first reductional division result in the formation of two types of metaphase II plates one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig.16).

The male chromosome formula is $9AA+Xy_p$.

During the course of present investigations the four species exhibited different chromosome numbers. Comparison with modal Polyphagan chromosome number ($2n = 20$) it exhibit trends towards increase in number. Cytologically family Histeridae is known by 26 species. Out of these eleven species exhibited the lowest number i.e. $2n = 20:9+Xy_p$ (Yadav and Dange, 1988, 1989, 1990; Dange, 1991 and the present report). All the species show Xy_p type of male sex chromosome system. Present investigations are new contribution to the cytology of this family. For the first time the highest diploid chromosome number in Histeridae i.e. $2n = 28$ is recorded in *Platysoma atratum* Er. and *Platysoma cambojensis* Mars.. During the course of present investigations the total chromosome length was found to be maximum in *Hister quadrimaculatus* L. (21.37μ) and minimum in *Platylister strialis* Mars. (12.19μ). All chromosomes show a gradual decrease in size. The X chromosome is smallest in *P. strialis* Mars. (0.68μ) and largest in *Platysoma cambojensis* Mars. (0.88μ). *P. cambojensis* Mars. has the largest y (0.81μ) whereas y was smallest in *H. quadrimaculatus* L. (0.58μ).

Comparative studies of the karyotypes of beetles are presented in table 1.

Table 1 : Karyotype analysis of four species of Histeridae beetles.

Sr. No.	Species	Chromosome pairs in percentage length														Length in μ			
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	x	y	TCL	x	y
1	<i>Hister quadrimaculatus</i> L.	10.3	10.12	9.87	9.56	9.34	9.22	8.85	8.21	7.67	7.33	6.56	5.12	-	3.56	2.8	23.73	0.74	0.58
2	<i>Platysoma cambojensis</i> Mars.	7.96	7.79	7.64	7.36	7.02	6.96	6.9	6.79	6.76	6.71	6.2	6.02	5.3	4.23	3.88	20.44	0.88	0.81
3	<i>Platysoma atratum</i> Er.	6.65	6.49	6.36	6.1	5.85	5.84	5.8	5.69	5.63	5.5	5.4	4.86	4.7	3.33	3.1	17.04	0.69	0.64
4	<i>Platylister strialis</i> Mars.	7.39	6.7	5.81	5.67	5.59	5.53	5.3	5.04	4.75	-	-	-	-	3.26	3.12	12.19	0.68	0.65

TCL = Total chromosome length.

Fig.1 Spermatogonial metaphase of *Hister quadrimaculatus* L.
Fig.2 Karyotype of the same
Fig.3 Spermatogonial metaphase of *Platysoma cambojensis* Mars.
Fig.4 Karyotype of the same
Fig.5 Spermatogonial metaphase of *P. atratum* Er.
Fig.6 Karyotype of the same
Fig.7 Spermatogonial metaphase *Platylister strialis* Mars.
Fig.8 Karyotype of the same
Fig.9 *Hister quadrimaculatus* L. (Metaphase I)
Fig.10 *H. quadrimaculatus* L. (Metaphase II)
Fig.11 *Platysoma cambojensis* Mars. (Metaphase I)
Fig.12 *P. cambojensis* Mars. (Metaphase II)
Fig.13 *P. atratum* Er. (Metaphase I)
Fig.14 *P. atratum* Er. (Metaphase II)
Fig.15 *Platylister strialis* Mars. (Metaphase I)
Fig.16 *P. strialis* Mars. (Metaphase II)

Conclusion

All four species studied show an Xy_p type of male sex chromosome mechanism, but differ in diploid numbers (20 to 28), chromosome morphology, and size. Two species (*P. cambojensis* and *P. atratum*) show the highest diploid number ($2n = 28$) reported so far in Histeridae. These findings provide new insights into chromosomal evolution in the family and significantly contribute to the cytogenetic knowledge of Coleoptera.

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